

THE FOUNDING OF THE UNIVERSITIES IN EUROPE AND MIDDLE EAST.

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Abstract:

This article provides brief information about the Oxford university and Ulugbek Madrasahs, which were among the first universities and madrasahs in Europe and Central Asia. Also, the article provides data on active construction of educational institutions, on the subjects that were taught at these universities, on multidisciplinary, higher educational and scientific institution in the Middle Ages. Clear data are provided comparing European universities and Central Asian madrasah.

Keywords: University, madrasah, Oxford, Central Asia, Europe, Ulugbek Madrasa, Astronomy, geometry, mathematics, Samarkand, research,

University (Latin universitas - assembly, complex) - a multidisciplinary, higher educational and scientific institution aimed at training highly qualified specialists in natural, social and humanitarian directions. It provides its graduates with in-depth theoretical preparation for future scientific, practical and pedagogical activities.

It makes a significant contribution to the integration of educational and scientific research work. It was the main distinctive feature of education. It corresponded to the highest (Madrasa or madrasa aliya (see: Madrasah) in the Muslim East. In the Middle East it was called dorilfunun.¹ The first university in Europe was usually considered to be the University of Bologna (Italy). This university was founded in 1088 and was known as one of the oldest higher education institutions in Europe. The University of Bologna played a major role in science, law and other fields and made a significant contribution to the development of scientific activity at that time.

One of the most famous and early universities in Europe was the University of Oxford.

The University of Oxford (English: University of Oxford; informally Oxford University or Oxford) was a large and ancient university located in England. It was the oldest university in the English-speaking world and the second oldest continuously existing university in the world. It was founded in 1096 in Oxford.

¹ O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi (2000-2005). P.(56 -58).

John Wycliffe, Thomas More, John Locke, and Robert Boyle taught at various times at the university.

trained specialists in theology, law, medicine, classical literature, modern and contemporary history, English language and literature, medieval and modern European languages and literature, oriental studies, physics, mathematics, biology, agricultural sciences, psychology, anthropology, geography, art history, and music. It had a number of specialized institutes and laboratories, and museums. The main library was founded in 1602. The year of the university's foundation is not known. In 1167, Henry II forbade foreign students from studying at the University of Paris. As a result, many English students were forced to leave France and study at Oxford University. The head of the university was the chancellor. Many officials contributed to the development of the university. The first of them was William Durham, who founded University College in 1249. He founded Balliol College in honor of the father of the future king of Scotland, John I de Balliol.

The English Lord Chancellor, Walter de Merton, developed regulations for colleges. This college served as a model for Cambridge College and other colleges in Oxford. At the same time, several universities were founded in Central Asia, which were called madrasas.

The University of Oxford in history also had its own motto, which distinguished it from other universities in history. The unique motto of this university is: *Dominus illuminatio mea* (The Lord is light).

Madrasah was an institution of higher learning. An educational building where, in addition to religious sciences, mathematics, rhetoric and logic, linguistics, law, philosophy, calligraphy, music, medicine, geography, astronomy and other sciences were taught.

From the Arabic language, madrasah a place where lessons were held. This term refers to educational buildings specially built for teaching. The first madrasah in Central Asia was the Ulugbek Madrasah in Samarkand. This madrasah was built in the 1420s by Mirzo Ulugbek. Ulugbek Madrasah served as an important center in the field of science, astronomy, mathematics and other sciences in its time. Scientific work was carried out in the madrasah, famous scientists studied, and many of those who studied here made a great contribution to the development of Central Asian science. Also, such qualified specialists worked and created in the Ulugbek madrasah. The Ulugbek Madrasah also played a significant role in the development of religious and scientific education in Central Asia. The Ulugbek Madrasah was an architectural monument in Samarkand. It was located to the west of the Registan ensemble. It was the first architectural monument built on Registan Square. It was considered a unique academy of the 15th century.²

² F. Abdukhalikov. Architectural epigraphy of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan today. 2015, P. 9.

This madrasah also attracted the attention of European scholars. The opinions of European scholars about the Ulugbek madrasah were highly valued, because it was a scientific and cultural center of great importance in its time. The achievements of the Ulugbek madrasah in astronomy, mathematics, geometry and other scientific fields also attracted great attention in Europe. Scientists working at the Ulugbek madrasah, including Ulugbek himself, conducted the most advanced astronomical research of their time.

Ulugbek established his own observatory in Samarkand in the 1420s and made very accurate measurements of astronomical objects. European astronomers, including Nicolaus Copernicus and Johannes Kepler, were inspired by Ulugbek's astronomical tables and reports. The astronomical table created by Ulugbek - "Zij-i Ulugbek" - was the most accurate astronomical table of the 15th century, widely distributed in Europe and recognized in particular by astronomers. This work proposed a very high-precision measurement of the positions and movements of astronomical objects and had a great influence on the development of astronomy in Europe.³

European scientists recognized the Ulugbek Madrasah was a center for scientific developments and education in its time. Not only religious, but also scientific education was provided there, which caused an influx of scientists and students from other countries to Samarkand. Influence in Europe: The educational system and scientific heritage of the Ulugbek Madrasah especially influenced the scientists of the Renaissance.

Many of them, for example, Copernicus and Kepler, studied the discoveries of Samarkand scientists and applied them in their work. Thus, the Ulugbek Madrasah had a great influence not only on the scientific development of Central Asia, but also on Europe. European scientists appreciated its scientific achievements and were inspired by it.

The famous poet, scientist and philosopher Abdurakhman Jami studied here.⁴ Among the students of the madrasa were the sheikh of the Naqshbandi order Khoja Ahrar and the poet Alisher Navoi. Lectures on mathematics, geometry, logic, natural sciences, theology, and philosophy were given at the educational institution. They were read by such famous scientists as Qadi Zada al-Rumi, Jamshid Ghiyath al-Din al-Kashi, Ali Qushchi, as well as Ulugbek himself. The first mudarris (rector) of the university was appointed Mawlana Muhammad Khavofi, who had deep scientific knowledge.⁵

³ Jaloliddin Akhmedov, teacher of the "Kokaldosh" secondary specialized Islamic educational institution. "Interfaith dialogue club". 2025. Students scientific conference. P.45.

⁴ Samarkand State University. Department of Samarkand Civilization History.

⁵ Movarounnahr ilmiy markazlari. Toshkent: O'zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi, 2022 — P. 480. ISBN 978-9943-7559-5-6.

In conclusion, the first universities and madrasas established in Europe and Central Asia were a great impetus for the development of today's universities. At the same time, the introduction of European education serves as a great impetus for the development of our country today. Ulugbek Madrasah made a great contribution to the development of science not only in Central Asia, but also in Europe, especially during the Renaissance. The first universities are the roots of modern science and contributed to the development of today's universities. The activities of our ancestors were great, their scientific heritage is priceless.

Reference

1. O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi (2000-2005) p(56-58).
2. F. Abdukhalikov. Architectural epigraphy of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan today. 2015, P. 9.
3. Jaloliddin Akhmedov, teacher of the "Kokaldosh" secondary specialized Islamic educational institution. “Interfaith dialogue club”. 2025. Students scientific conference. P.45.
4. Samarkand State University. Department of Samarkand Civilization History.
5. Movarounnahr ilmiy markazlari. Toshkent: O‘zbekiston xalqaro islom akademiyasi, 2022 — P. 480. ISBN 978-9943-7559-5-6.